

SPECIFIC FEATURES OF JACK LONDON'S STORY.

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Abstract: The article presents Jack London's view on the poetics of story genre. Attention is paid to determining the place of the story in the literary process of the early 20th century, the relationship between the concepts «form» and «style», fact and fiction. The author also dwells on the important in London's understanding question about the features of the composite structure, expressing the author's position, perspective, creating an atmosphere of action in the story, and the importance of the formation of the author's style.

Аннотация: В статье представлена позиция Джека Лондона относительно поэтики жанра рассказа. Акцентируется внимание на определении писателем места рассказа в литературном процессе начала XX века, соотношении понятий «форма» и «стиль», факт и вымысел. Уделяется внимание важному, в понимании Лондона, вопросу об особенностях композиционной структуры, выражения авторской позиции, точки зрения, создания атмосферы действия в рассказе, а также важности формирования авторского стиля.

Key words: the genre, the art form, content, author, writer, composition, perspective, style.

Ключевые слова: жанр, художественная форма, содержание, автор, писатель, композиция, точка зрения, стиль

Jack London was born in 1876 in San Francisco. His real name was John Griffit. His father was a farmer. The family was extremely poor and the boy had to earn his living after school. He sold newspapers, worked at a factory. Later he became a sailor; during some time he wandered vrith the unemployed. For a year he attended the Oakland High school and spent a semester at the University of California, but as he had no money he had to stop his studies and went to work again.

This time it was a laundry. In 1897 he went to the Klondike as a gold miner. His first short story was published in 1898. Some of the difficulties he met during the first years of his literary work are described in his novel "Martin Eden".

During the sixteen years of his literary career Jack London published about fifty books: short stories, novels and essays. In his best stories London described the severe life and struggle of people against nature. He died at the age of forty in 1916.

Jack London, a recognized master of the short story genre, can rightly be called the writer who opened the 20th century in US literature. Beginning with W. Irving, American writers improved the form of the story, paying attention to the issues of poetics, the formation of genre canons, taking into account European traditions, as well as national cultural specifics. Inheriting the traditions of its predecessors, London, according to the American literary critic L.A. Berkov, it was in this genre that he most obviously "experimented with ideas and techniques."

He wrote more than 200 stories (160 of them were included in 19 collections), in relation to which two genre definitions are used in American London studies - story and tale; Russian scientists also do not dwell on the specifics of the national genre form, using the term "story".

Jack London in the article "Features of Literary Development" (1900) analyzes the relevance of the story genre for the contemporary era: tracing the connection between the processes of civilization formation in new historical conditions and the main trends in the development of literature, he comes to the conclusion that the new time requires new literature, poses new challenges for the writer. In his discussions about the laws of literary creativity, London often refers to the authority of recognized masters of the genre of short stories, both American and European. So, referring to the stories of American (E.A. Poe, A. Beers and others) and English (R.L. Stevenson, R. Haggardid and others) writers in the article "The Terrible and Tragic in Fiction" (1903), London develops the idea of the important role of the "tragic and terrible" in the plot of the story, since "only shocks make the deepest strings of human nature sound..."

London in his stories presents a private history of life in the context of epoch-making events - in the fate of a person, the writer sees the fate of the country and the entire human civilization. This circumstance allows us to talk about London's desire to create a special subtext that reveals the author's worldview position: "I found a plot-thesis, and my story sometimes had a subtext. On the surface there is a simple story, understandable to a child, full of action, movement, colors, and below it is a real story, philosophical, complex, full of meaning. One reader gets a fascinating story, the other one gets my philosophy of life"

The artistic image of the world in his stories reflects the consciousness of a romantic writer, for whom it is important to express emotions, feelings, and a realist writer, who analyzes the causes of what is happening, striving for broad, historically determined generalizations.

The most important artistic principle of the London narrator is from the particular to the general: "To be truthful, to be artistically accurate, you must turn to the particular, through the particular to the universal" In London's stories, as a rule, the hero's point of view is the main one, in most cases realized in the form of improperly direct speech, which makes it possible to detect the author's position, along with the author's journalistic or philosophical digressions, which determines a special pathos, which becomes an important component. artistic idea of the work. So, in the cycle of "Northern Tales", the objectivity of what is depicted is given by the presence of three points of view on events: the view of a white man who has not lost touch with the world of civilization; the look of a white man who has adopted new laws of life in the North (outside and inside); the view of an indigenous inhabitant of the northern world - an Indian, an Eskimo.

Thanks to this device, a polyphony of individual perceptions arises in the stories; From the conjugation of the different positions of the characters, the author's worldview becomes apparent regarding the dialectic of the process of formation of a new civilizational formation in the conditions of the life of the North.

In a number of letters, London expresses the idea that the success of any story, in addition to a successful plot basis, depends on stylistic perfection, the degree of authorial skill. Answering one of the questions in a questionnaire addressed by the Editor magazine to several famous writers of the time, London noted that "a well-written story with a poor plot is preferable to a badly written strong plot"

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